

the human capital, leadership and innovation from new firm.

BOUROUAHA Abdelhammid *

Abdurrahman Mira university,
Bejaia

BOUREDJA Sara**

Abdelhammid Ibn Badis university,
Mostaganem**Abstract:**

The innovation field faced an important growth in the latest years according to their importance in the both microeconomic and macroeconomic level. The most important for us is the microeconomic one. The human capital is the engine of the creation in the firm, and the leaders are the creators of the innovation wave in the firm. In this paper, we try to clarify the relation between the human capital, leadership to push the firms to innovate and to sustain in the innovation.

Keywords: Innovation, human capital, leadership, sustainable.

الملخص:

الابداع مجال يشهد نمو ملحوظ في الآونة الأخيرة و هذا بفضل اهميته على المستويين الجزئي و الكلي، و الذي يهمننا في دراستنا هو المستوى الجزئي، و راس المال البشري من اهم محركات الصنع في المؤسسة، و من اهم راس المال البشري، نجد ان القادة هم موجدوا موجة الابداع في المؤسسة، في هذه الورقة البحثية العلاقة بين راس المال البشري، القيادة و لدفع الابداع داخل المؤسسة و للاستدامة على الابداع،

الكلمات المفتاحية: ابداع، راس مال بشري، قيادة ، استدامة.

** bouredjasara@gmail.com

* b.abdelhammid@gmail.com

Introduction:

Following the technological growth, there is huge changes in the desirous of the customers due to this growth. To satisfy this desirous, the enterprises must follow this technological growth in the first, and to survive for a long time, and to get the ability to create more product or give more services for the customer following the sustainable technological change third. All this movement are due the technological change. This latest is appeared in the face of innovation. But this latest seen much better in the small firms rather than the small ones because the role of, innovation appeared better in small firms rather than the big one, and following (Jovanovic 2001, 54,55), “The new economy is one in which technologies and products become obsolete at a much faster rate but now the process is faster, partly because the technology is mature. It is clear that we are entering the era of the young firm. The average age of all companies in the stock market – and the average age of the giants – is shrinking as well. Since the death rate of old capital is higher, this means that the “birth rate” of new capital must rise if we are to maintain the stock of existing capital at existing levels. The small firm will thus resume a role that, in its importance, is greater than it has been at any time in the last seventy years or so”. Also, the innovation has an important role for the enterprise. This latest does not means that all the enterprises could innovate. The ability of the innovation is affected with different external variables and internal variable that are called the inputs of innovation. This inputs are also obstacles of the firms does not have them. the different obstacles that it faces the enterprises to innovation, different drivers of innovation. As a beginning, we cannot think for a world without innovation, according to (Cheng, Chang, and Li 2013a), Innovation is a key factor that it influences the viability of the firms in addition to trigger social and economic change.

The innovation is the main important key for the economic success according to different economists such as (Hamel and Getz 2004). In the another side, the ability to innovate is fundamental to sustain competitive advantage (C.-J. Chen and Huang 2010).

There is different definition of innovation that are turn around the same hub, according to (Schumpeter 2006),” the innovation is a process and outcomes of creating something new, which is also of value”, according to (Porter and Scott Stern 2001),” innovation is a new way of doing things which is commercialized. The process of innovation cannot be separated from firm’s strategic and competitive context...”.Also, according to (Levitt 2002),” to be innovative, an idea must be creative and must be implemented”.

Both of Ronaldo Mota and David Scott in the book of Education for Innovation and Independent Learning suggest that the best way to connect the economic development with sustainable social development is by adopting innovatory strategies (Mota and Scott 2014, 21).

We can say that innovation affect the society in the both sides: good side and worst side. According to (Joseph Alois Schumpeter 1961), while the innovation was a creative and beneficial, that is bring new things , new products , new ideas , new designs, that it could generate wealth , employment and high level of life, it could also destroy the existing products, existing enterprises and technologies with a latest result to destroy economies and push unemployment.

This paper is organized as follows, section 2 reviews the literatures on human capital, section 3 introduces the innovation, section for describes the innovation and leadership and different types of innovation, the main results and discussion are presented in the section5 in table that present the factors that hamper the innovation. The section 6 conclude the papers with best recommendation and future research.

Literature review:

Human capital:

The necessity of the human capital:

According to the (Benhabib and Spiegel 1994, 166),” the accumulation of the human capital is considered as an important factor for the economic development”. Following the results of this study, they found that the human capital has an indirect effect of the economic growth following its effect on the growth of the total factor of productivity in two mechanisms. In the first mechanism, the gathered results show that the human capital influence directly the rate of domestically produced technological innovation. Where in the second mechanism, they find that the human capital stock affects the speed of the adoption of technology from abroad.

In the field of innovation and following a discussion of Mr. CHANDRAJIT Banerjee¹,” the fundamental driver behind any innovation process is the human factor associated with it... Other factors, such as technology and capital, also influence the innovation process; these directly correlate with the human factor”(Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014). And from the factors to launch the foster the innovation in a firm Following the results gathered from the studies of (Bauernschuster, Falck, and Heblich 2009, 331), the continuous training of workers is positively correlated with the firm’s innovation. Following the study of (Galia and Legros 2004, 2), the important assets of innovative firms are employees, competencies and knowledge. The human capital is the key determinant of the innovation process (Bauernschuster, Falck, and Heblich 2009). According to (Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent 2014, 6) who said that the “the educated people make good innovators, thus educations speeds the process of the technological diffusion”,

In the macroeconomic side and following the research of (Pelinescu 2015, 184), it is difficult to believe that EU 2020 could achieve their goals presented in the area of growth: smart, sustainable and inclusive without a good education and training system.

Practice related with human resources:

From the major goals of every enterprise is to sustain for long period in front of the different environmental changes in the PLESCTE.

According to (Neto and Jabbour 2010), “the Sustainable innovation will not be realistic in the absence of the human resources”.

The practice plays an important role in the sustainable innovation. According to (Theyel 2000), “the companies who are leaders in environmental innovation widely practice environmental training and incentive programs to involve their employees in continuous innovation”.

Through (Sarkis, Gonzalez-Torre, and Adenso-Diaz 2010), they said “through the training, the organizational capacities and knowledge of the workers are developed, thus employees could understand how the environment will affect and be affected by their duties and decision”.

The R&D play an important role in the enterprise because the enterprises improve their product to cope with current and future demand.

Human capital and innovation:

The is an important relationship between the human capital and the innovation in the firm. In the process of the production inside the enterprise, the labor force is as the engine of the production, because we see the necessity of the person in all level of production. Following the importance of the innovation in the firm, from the first generator of the innovation in the firm is the employees because the racings of the innovation starts from an idea in the mind of the employee. There for, firm with an important human capital is able to innovate better than the firms with low human capital. Following the study of (Kato, Okamuro, and Honjo 2015), the human capital of the firm could boost the R&D in the firm that will generate innovation outcomes for the firms.

¹ Director General of Confederation of Indian Industry

Innovation:

The importance of the innovation:

Following the new appearance of innovation, there are many studies and many authors tried to give a clear and global definition of innovation. From the first side and according to (Renning 2000), "the source of innovation is the Latin word Novus which means new. It is referred sometimes as new idea, new method or new device or the process of creating something new. From another side, the Innovation is a continuous process (OECD 2005, 15). Also, Innovation is the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business practices, workplace organization or external relations. Following the studies of (Pavitt and Walker 1976; Kim 1980; Archibugi, Cesaratto, and Sirilli 1991; Ernst and Kim 2002; Guan and Chen 2012), "the innovation could be defined also as major stimulus to national economic growth in the different categories of economies (industrial, newly industrialized and the developing economies)". Innovation is central to the growth of output and productivity. In the neoclassical view and according to (Sutton and Klein 2003) and (OECD 2005, 30) the innovation is an asset of creation, for that it is an aspect of business cycle.

The importance of the innovation characterized in different ways, where the new forms of innovation could be the drives of the economic development for all regions. According to (Nelson and Winter 1982), "the innovation is a path-dependent process whereby knowledge and technology are developed through interaction between various actors and other factors".

Innovation is defined also as a system emphasizes the importance of the transfer and the diffusion of ideas, skills, knowledge, information and the signals of many kinds between persons, activities and department in the society and indeed in the organizations. It can be defined also as a dynamic process in which knowledge is accumulated through learning and interaction. From this latest definition, the diffusion of knowledge between workers seems from the important ways that foster the innovation in the organization.

Leadership and innovation:

The leaders from the important persons in the human capital of firms because they create and the movement to grow with the enterprise. Following the study of (Sariol and Abebe 2017), the CEOs has an important role in shaping the innovative agenda of the firm. In addition and according to (Scherr and Jensen 2007), the leadership consist for four critical, element:

The best leadership create a vision for the future that represent a significant departure from the past,

The best leadership create a system that facilitates enrollment into and elicits voluntary commitment to the vision by the critical mass of people required to discover and implement the breakthroughs required for realization of the vision.

According to the study of (Gumusluoglu and İlsev 2007), "the leadership has been suggested to be an important factor that it affect the innovation". As a result of the study of (Gumusluoglu and İlsev 2007), the transformational leadership is an important determinants of organizational innovation. In addition, it encourages the managers to engage in transformational leadership behaviors in order to promote organizational innovation. In addition, he found that the external support can be more important to boost innovation than the internal support.

Levels of innovation:

There are different characteristics to select the levels of the innovations. The most appeared character is the levels of innovation of product or service in the market. Following the report of (OECD 2009, 12), there are three level of innovation:

New to the firm:

This level of innovation includes all new things such as procedures, technics ...etc. these new things were in the market and in the other enterprises but new in our enterprises.

New to the market:

This level contains the new things for our market, but it was exit in the other market

New to the world:

It is the most important level because it brings new things that did not exist before.

Kinds of innovation:

According to (Dodgson and Gann 2010), there are two kinds of innovation:

Incremental innovation:

The incremental innovation characterized in the new improvement that are coming from new ideas, to an existing product, service or even a process of execution.

Breakthrough innovation:

These kinds of innovation appear when the innovative product inter to a new market.

The radical (transformational) innovation:

We say that this is a Radical Innovation where the nature of the product service or the process was changed.

To explain these two previous parts for the innovation (levels, kinds), the figure below represents the both of levels and kinds of innovation and show the relationship between them:

Figure 1:levels of innovation

source: edited by the authors

Sources of innovation:

From the important sources of innovation and new things to the society is the institution of learning and education in general and especially universities according to the different activities that it enhances to develop the society. The universities and Research and development institute play an important role for innovation ecosphere. According to (Youtie and Shapira 2008), the traditional universities were as a storehouse of old knowledge, where the modern universities is seeing as generator of technological innovation or economic development in its region.

Types of innovation:

There are four types of innovation segmented to two different types, technological innovation and non-technological innovation. In the figure below, we try to give different type of innovation:

Figure 2: different types of innovation

Source: (OECD 2005)

As we seen in the figure above, there are two big kind of innovation, technological innovation and non-technological innovation. Each type of these innovation also divided to two types according to the goals want to achieve.

Starting with the technological innovation, there will be two types of innovation that they use technology:

Technological innovation:

According to (Krishnaswamy, Mathirajan, and Bala Subrahmanya 2014), the activities use technology according to its important in innovation. Because, there are the activities that it uses technology, so in this time we will find technological innovation, that is mean we use technology to innovate. Therefore, we will see touch

this kind of innovation in two places, the product or service from a side and the process of producing the product or giving the service.

The product innovation:

In the way of bringing innovation into the level of the product, the innovation in the product will be realized in following some important procedures (Cheng, Chang, and Li 2013b):

In the first, we find that improving in technical specification as design, this kind of improvement need technology. To compare it with the kinds of innovation, we find that this is one of the incremental innovation because it keeps the characteristics of the product.

From the important ways of innovation that are used in the level of product is by improving the component and materials

Using an incorporated software from the important technological innovation used in the level of the product for the result of innovating the product.

The process innovation:

In a hand, the process innovation characterized in the different procedures used to achieve the innovation in the process of the production (Ivanov and Avasilcăi 2014). From the second hand, the innovation did not focus just in the product, but for all the processes of the creation from the idea to the ways of selling the product or service. In this point, we can find three important point of the process innovation as it shown in the figure:

Changes in techniques:

These techniques characterized in the different changes in the process, these technics may be will reduce from the consumption of the energy, reduce the time of the process pf production or distribution.

Changes in equipment:

With using new equipment for the procedure of innovation and these, equipment's will be of course equipment's with high technology.

Changes in software:

From the newest method of implementing innovation in the enterprise is following the technological development and changes and using new software that will facilitate any procedure that was take many time to be executed in a short time with less consumption of energy and raw material with a high quality and less level of wastes.

Non-technological innovation:

The second part are the activities that it do not use technology According to (Hyard 2013), so it is not technological innovation, and we will touch this kind of innovation in both of organizational and marketing innovation. Why? because it does need technology in the activity. From this point, we can suggest, there will be a clarification in the meaning of the innovation, where in the first, we think that innovation is always related with technology, se in the activities that it does not use technology machines or materials; we cannot think that it will be able to be innovated.

To more clarify the different types of the innovation and what they need to be innovated, the figure bellow presents this context in two different types of innovation separated in the term of using technology, so there will

be technological innovation and non-technological innovation. These two types of innovation will be divided to the number of types supposed for each type.

For the non-technological innovation, we found there are two other types of innovation that did not need technology to be innovated. These are:

The marketing innovation:

According to (Halpern 2010), Marketing is an important activity for the enterprises, according to its role from the creation of the product until selling it. In addition, by using innovated method as it shown in the figure below, it will be an innovated activity or marketing innovation.

Figure 3: innovation and four Ps

Source:(OECD 2005)

These innovated activities could be segmented through the four Ps as it shown above in addition to use other new methods such as:

Implementing new marketing method,

Involving significant changes in products,

Involving changes in promotion, pricing ... etc.

The organizational innovation:

According to the different exchanges between enterprise and organization, The organization get an important role in the performance on the enterprise (Camisón and Villar-López 2014). According to (Laforet 2013), the organizational innovation has a greater impact on the small and medium sized enterprises.

Sustainable innovation:

They are different expressions mean the sustainable innovation such as eco innovation, environmentally driven innovation and green innovation but it is for the same definition, that is one approach where the firms could adopt in becoming greener and yet competitive(Fadhilah and Ramayah 2012).

From the important factors that suggest for sustainable innovation is demanding for environmentally product and service because of the environmental degradation. This latest push the organization to be more ecologically

sensitive in the side of opening new opportunities to innovate in sustainable manner (Fadhilah and Ramayah 2012).

According to different studies as (Theyel 2000), the enterprises that their innovation in a sustainable manner could reap economic and environmental benefits. The firms being green, the planet could preserve their natural resources for the future generation. From another side where different authors such as (Fawzi Halila 2007) in his doctoral thesis, he found that SI contributes also in Reduction in air emission, resource consumption; and consumption of hazardous materials.

Drivers for sustainable innovation:

from the different factors that enhance the sustainable innovation, there are:

Different studies such as (Berrone et al. 2007), (Brunnermeier and Cohen 2003) find that **Regulation** from the important factor for sustainable innovation.

(Zhu and Sarkis 2007) find that **market demand** plays an important role in the sustainable innovation.

Some studies as (Y.-S. Chen 2008), (Neto and Jabbour 2010) , (Ramus 2002) and find that **Firm internal factors** from the important factors for sustainable innovation.

Studies in the level of the enterprise or national policy level

Management practices

Different obstacles for sustainable innovation SI:

Find financing resources as venture capital

To attack the problem, according to (Stringer 2000),”the innovator should follow some strategies such as:

Make break through innovation a strategic and cultural priority,

Hire more creative and innovative people,

Grow informal project laboratories within the traditional organization,

Create “idea markets” within the organization,

Become an “ambidextrous organization”

Experiment with acquisition, JVs, cooperative ventures, and alliances with outside innovative entities,

Engage in corporate venturing

Establish a corporate venture capital fund,

Participate in an “emerging industry fund” EIF

According to (Bhidé 2006),”From the important factor that it enhance the enterprise to innovation in the side of the entrepreneurial activity and the research and development policies, the willingness of the customer to try, discover and use the new products and services which it called also ‘Venturesome consumption’

Factors hampering innovation activities:

Following different studies on innovation, the researchers of OECD try to globalize the important factors that hamper the innovation activities in the firm.

These factors are as follows:

Cost factors: this factor summarize the different factors that has a relation with the cost of the activities to innovate.

Knowledge factors: this factor is relation with the knowledge factors that hamper the firm to innovate.

Market factors: this factor summarize the factors related with the market such as offer and demand.

Institutional factors: this factor globalize the factors related with the institution of the government.

Other reasons: this factor globalize the other different reasons that hamper innovation. After selecting the different factors, they segment this factors in the four different types of innovation that are: product innovation, process innovation, organizational innovation and marketing innovation. This segmentation helps the leaders of the firms to look for the points of hamper to look for solution.

These factors are presented in the table below:

Table 1: Factors hampering innovation activities

Relevant for:	Product innovation	Process innovation	Organizational innovation	Marketing innovation
Cost factors				
Excessive perceived risks	*	*	*	*
Cost too high	*	*	*	*
Lack of funds within the enterprises	*	*	*	*
<u>Lack of finance from sources outside the enterprise</u>				
Venture capital	*	*	*	*
Public sources of funding	*	*	*	*
Knowledge factors				
Innovation potentiel (R&D, design, etc.) insufficient	*	*		*
<u>Lack of finance from sources outside the enterprise:</u>				
Within the enterprise	*	*		*
In the labor market	*	*		*
Lack of information in technology	*	*		
Lack of information in market	*			*
Deficiencies in the availability of external services	*	*	*	*
<u>Difficulty in finding co-operation partners for:</u>				
Product or process development	*	*		
Marketing partnerships				*
<u>Organizational rigidities within the enterprise:</u>				
Attitude of personal towards change	*	*	*	*
Attitude of managers towards change	*	*	*	*
Managerial structure of enterprise	*	*	*	*
Inability to devote staff to innovation activity due to production requirements	*	*		
Market factors:				
Uncertain demand for innovative goods or services	*			*
Potential market dominated by established enterprises	*			*
Institutional factors:				
Lack of infrastructure	*	*		*
Weakness of property rights	*			*
Legislation, regulations, standards, taxation	*			*

Other reasons for not innovating:				
No need to innovate due to earlier innovation	*	*	*	*
No need because of lack of demand for innovation	*			*

Source: (OECD 2005, 113)

Factors related with the objectives and the effect of innovation on the firm:

Table 2: factors relating to the objectives and effects of innovation

Relevant for:	Product innovation	Process innovation	Organizational innovation	Marketing innovation
Competition, demand and markets:				
Replace products being phased out	*			
Increase range of goods and services	*			
Develop environment-friendly products	*			
Increase or maintain market share	*			*
Enter new markets	*			*
Increase visibility or exposure for products				*
Reduced time to respond to customer needs		*	*	
Production and delivery				
Improve quality of goods and services	*	*	*	
Improve flexibility of production or service provision		*	*	
Increase capacity of production or service provision		*	*	
Reduce unit labor costs		*	*	
Reduce consumption of materials and energy	*	*	*	
Reduce product design cost		*	*	
Reduce production lead times		*	*	
Achieve industry technical standards	*	*	*	
Reduce operating cost for service provision		*	*	
Increase efficiency or speed of supplying and/or delivering goods and services		*	*	
Improve IT capabilities		*	*	
Workplace organization				
Improve communication and interaction among different business activities			*	

Increase sharing or transferring of knowledge with other organizations			*	
Increase the ability to adapt to different client demands			*	*
Develop stronger relationships with customers			*	*
Improve working condition		*	*	
Other				
Reduce environmental impacts or improve health and safety	*	*	*	
Meet regulatory requirements	*	*	*	

Source: (OECD 2005, 108)

Conclusion:

The firm is the important unit in the economy. This unit has the ability to move up with the economy as a whole because it create and product. This production is due to another engine that is the human capital. So, the human capital is the important capital in the firm, because it is the engine of the operation and the process of production. In the human capital, there are the leaders. The leaders in the firm has the important effect because they push the employees in an intelligent manner to work and produce more, in addition to work as a group.

An addition, from the important movement for the firm following the latest studies is the innovation because it's the key for the sustainable growth. Therefore, the leadership with the innovation spirit create the wave of the innovation in the firm. the human capital. There for, the leadership play an important role in boosting the human capital in the firm to innovate and to survive.

References:

- Archibugi, Daniele, Sergio Cesaratto, and Giorgio Sirilli. 1991. "Sources of Innovative Activities and Industrial Organization in Italy." *Research Policy* 20 (4): 299–313. doi:10.1016/0048-7333(91)90091-4.
- Bauernschuster, Stefan, Oliver Falck, and Stephan Heblich. 2009. "Training and Innovation." *Journal of Human Capital* 3 (4): 323–53. doi:10.1086/653713.
- Benhabib, Jess, and Mark M. Spiegel. 1994. "The Role of Human Capital in Economic Development Evidence from Aggregate Cross-Country Data." *Journal of Monetary Economics* 34 (2): 143–73. doi:10.1016/0304-3932(94)90047-7.
- Berrone, Pascual, Liliana Gelabert, Andrea Fosfuri, and Luis R. Gomez-Mejia. 2007. "Can Institutional Forces Create Competitive Advantage? An Empirical Examination of Environmental Innovation." IESE Research Paper D/723. IESE Business School. <http://ideas.repec.org/p/ebg/iesewp/d-0723.html>.
- Bhidé, Amar. 2006. "Venturesome Consumption, Innovation, and Globalization." In *Perspectives on the Performance of the Continental Economies*, edited by Edmund S. Phelps and Hans-Werner Sinn, 169–222. The MIT Press. <http://mitpress.universitypressscholarship.com/view/10.7551/mitpress/9780262015318.001.001/upso-9780262015318-chapter-7>.
- Brunnermeier, Smita B, and Mark A Cohen. 2003. "Determinants of Environmental Innovation in US Manufacturing Industries." *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management* 45 (2): 278–93. doi:10.1016/S0095-0696(02)00058-X.
- Camisón, César, and Ana Villar-López. 2014. "Organizational Innovation as an Enabler of Technological Innovation Capabilities and Firm Performance." *Journal of Business Research* 67 (1): 2891–2902. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.06.004.
- Chen, Chung-Jen, and Yi-Fen Huang. 2010. "Creative Workforce Density, Organizational Slack, and Innovation Performance." *Journal of Business Research* 63 (4): 411–17. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.03.018.
- Chen, Yu-Shan. 2008. "The Driver of Green Innovation and Green Image – Green Core Competence." *Journal of Business Ethics* 81 (3): 531–43. doi:10.1007/s10551-007-9522-1.
- Cheng, Cheng-Feng, Man-Ling Chang, and Chu-Shiu Li. 2013a. "Configural Paths to Successful Product Innovation." *Journal of Business Research* 66 (12): 2561–73. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.10.006.

- . 2013b. “Configural Paths to Successful Product Innovation.” *Journal of Business Research* 66 (12): 2561–73. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.10.006.
- Dodgson, Mark, and David Gann. 2010. *Innovation: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford ; New York: Oxford University Press.
- Ernst, Dieter, and Linsu Kim. 2002. “Global Production Networks, Knowledge Diffusion, and Local Capability Formation.” *Research Policy*, NELSON + WINTER + 20, 31 (8–9): 1417–29. doi:10.1016/S0048-7333(02)00072-0.
- Fadhilah, Z., and T. Ramayah. 2012. “Behind the Green Doors: What Management Practices Lead to Sustainable Innovation?” *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, International Congress on Interdisciplinary Business and Social Sciences 2012 (ICIBSoS 2012), 65 (December): 247–52. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.118.
- Fawzi Halila. 2007. “The Adoption and Diffusion of Environmental Innovations.” Doctoral thesis, Luleå University of Technology. www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:344951/FULLTEXT01.pdf.
- Galia, Fabrice, and Diego Legros. 2004. “Research and Development, Innovation, Training, Quality and Profitability: Evidence from France.” SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 633973. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=633973>.
- Guan, Jiancheng, and Kaihua Chen. 2012. “Modeling the Relative Efficiency of National Innovation Systems.” *Research Policy* 41 (1): 102–15. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2011.07.001.
- Gumusluoglu, Lale, and Arzu İlsev. 2007. “Transformational Leadership and Organizational Innovation: The Roles of Internal and External Support for Innovation.” SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 1068142. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1068142>.
- Halpern, Nigel. 2010. “Marketing Innovation: Sources, Capabilities and Consequences at Airports in Europe’s Peripheral Areas.” *Journal of Air Transport Management*, Selected Papers from the Air Transport Research Society Conference Athens, 2008, 16 (2): 52–58. doi:10.1016/j.jairtraman.2009.10.002.
- Hamel, Gary, and Gary Getz. 2004. “Funding Growth in an Age of Austerity.” *Harvard Business Review* 82 (7–8): 76–84, 186.
- Hyard, Alexandra. 2013. “Non-Technological Innovations for Sustainable Transport.” *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 80 (7): 1375–86. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2012.11.009.

- Ivanov, Cristian-Ionuț, and Silvia Avasilcăi. 2014. "Measuring the Performance of Innovation Processes: A Balanced Scorecard Perspective." *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2nd World Conference on Business, Economics and Management, 109 (January): 1190–93. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.610.
- Joseph Alois Schumpeter. 1961. *The Theory of Economic Development: An Inquiry Into Profits, Capital, Credit, Interest, and the Business Cycle*. Transaction Publishers.
- Jovanovic, Boyan. 2001. "New Technology and The Small Firm." *Small Business Economics* 16 (1): 53–56. doi:10.1023/A:1011132809150.
- Kato, Masatoshi, Hiroyuki Okamuro, and Yuji Honjo. 2015. "Does Founders' Human Capital Matter for Innovation? Evidence from Japanese Start-Ups." *Journal of Small Business Management* 53 (1): 114–28. doi:10.1111/jsbm.12094.
- Kim, Linsu. 1980. "Organizational Innovation and Structure." *Journal of Business Research* 8 (2): 225–45. doi:10.1016/0148-2963(80)90012-0.
- Krishnaswamy, K. N., M. Mathirajan, and M. H. Bala Subrahmanya. 2014. "Technological Innovations and Its Influence on the Growth of Auto Component SMEs of Bangalore: A Case Study Approach." *Technology in Society* 38 (August): 18–31. doi:10.1016/j.techsoc.2014.01.001.
- Laforet, Sylvie. 2013. "Organizational Innovation Outcomes in SMEs: Effects of Age, Size, and Sector." *Journal of World Business* 48 (4): 490–502. doi:10.1016/j.jwb.2012.09.005.
- Levitt, Theodore. 2002. "Creativity Is Not Enough." *Harvard Business Review* 80 (8): 137–44.
- Mota, Ronaldo, and David Scott. 2014. "Chapter 3 - Innovation." In *Education for Innovation and Independent Learning*, edited by Ronaldo Mota and David Scott, 21–40. San Diego: Elsevier. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B978012800847800003X>.
- Nelson, Richard R., and Sidney G. Winter. 1982. *An Evolutionary Theory of Economic Change*. Cambridge, Mass.: Belknap Press. <https://www.amazon.com/Evolutionary-Theory-Economic-Change-Belknap/dp/0674272285>.
- Neto, Angelo Saturnino, and Charbel Jose Chiappetta Jabbour. 2010. "Guidelines for Improving the Adoption of Cleaner Production in Companies through Attention to Non-Technical Factors: A Literature Review." *African Journal of Business Management* 4 (19): 4217–29.
- OECD. 2005. *Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data, 3rd Edition*. Third. Luxembourg.

<http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/oslomanualguidelinesforcollectingandinterpretinginnovationdata3rdedition.htm>.

———. 2009. *Innovation in Firms: A Microeconomic Perspective*. OECD Innovation Strategy. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/book/9789264056213-en>.

Pavitt, K., and W. Walker. 1976. "Government Policies towards Industrial Innovation: A Review." *Research Policy* 5 (1): 11–97. doi:10.1016/0048-7333(76)90017-2.

Pelinescu, Elena. 2015. "The Impact of Human Capital on Economic Growth." *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 2nd International Conference "Economic Scientific Research - Theoretical, Empirical and Practical Approaches", ESPERA 2014, 13-14 November 2014, Bucharest, Romania, 22: 184–90. doi:10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00258-0.

Porter, Michael E, and Scott Stern. 2001. "Innovation: Location Matters." *MIT Sloan Management Review* 42 (4). <http://www.hbs.edu/faculty/Pages/item.aspx?num=10690>.

Ramus, Catherine A. 2002. "Encouraging Innovative Environmental Actions: What Companies and Managers Must Do." *Journal of World Business* 37 (2): 151–64. doi:10.1016/S1090-9516(02)00074-3.

Rennings, Klaus. 2000. "Redefining Innovation — Eco-Innovation Research and the Contribution from Ecological Economics." *Ecological Economics* 32 (2): 319–32. doi:10.1016/S0921-8009(99)00112-3.

Sariol, Ana M., and Michael A. Abebe. 2017. "The Influence of CEO Power on Explorative and Exploitative Organizational Innovation." *Journal of Business Research* 73 (April): 38–45. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.11.016.

Sarkis, Joseph, Pilar Gonzalez-Torre, and Belarmino Adenso-Diaz. 2010. "Stakeholder Pressure and the Adoption of Environmental Practices: The Mediating Effect of Training." *Journal of Operations Management* 28 (2): 163–76. doi:10.1016/j.jom.2009.10.001.

Scherr, Allan L., and Michael C. Jensen. 2007. "A New Model of Leadership." SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 920623. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=920623>.

Schumpeter, Joseph. 2006. *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*. New Ed edition. London; New York: Routledge.

Soumitra Dutta, Bruno Lanvin, and Sacha Wunsch-Vincent. 2014. "The Global Innovation Index 2014: The Human Factor in Innovation." Global Innovation Index GII 2014. Global

Innovation Index. INSEAD.

http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/economics/gii/gii_2014.pdf.

Stringer, Robert. 2000. "How To Manage Radical Innovation." *California Management Review* 42 (4): 70–88. doi:10.2307/41166054.

Sutton, Dave, and Tom Klein. 2003. *Enterprise Marketing Management: The New Science of Marketing*. 1 edition. Hoboken, N.J: Wiley.

Theyel, Gregory. 2000. "Management Practices for Environmental Innovation and Performance." *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 20 (2): 249–66. doi:10.1108/01443570010304288.

Youtie, Jan, and Philip Shapira. 2008. "Building an Innovation Hub: A Case Study of the Transformation of University Roles in Regional Technological and Economic Development." *Research Policy*, Special Section on University-Industry Linkages: The Significance of Tacit Knowledge and the Role of Intermediaries, 37 (8): 1188–1204. doi:10.1016/j.respol.2008.04.012.

Zhu, Qinghua, and Joseph Sarkis. 2007. "The Moderating Effects of Institutional Pressures on Emergent Green Supply Chain Practices and Performance." *International Journal of Production Research* 45 (18–19): 4333–55. doi:10.1080/00207540701440345.